

Li-Fi – THE FUTURE OPTICAL WIRELESS COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGY

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Abstract:

The world is revolutionized by the use of internet. There is an exponential growth in the number of users accessing the internet. Thus the number of devices that use wireless communication has also increased leading to more network complexity, wireless radio bandwidth shortage and an increased risk of interference of radio frequencies. Li-Fi (Light Fidelity) - the Future of Wireless Communication is a solution to this increasing demand for speed, security and reliability. Li-Fi technology proposed by Dr. Harald Haas , transmits “Data through illumination” . LED light bulbs are used as the mode of communication . Li-Fi is ideal for high density wireless data coverage in confined area. Li-Fi provides better efficiency ,bandwidth, availability and security than Wi-Fi. By utilizing the low-cost nature of LEDs and lighting units, there are various opportunities to exploit in this medium, from public internet access to auto-piloted cars that communicate through their headlights. Data for laptops, smart phones, and tablets can be transmitted through light in a room in near future.

Keywords—Li-Fi, Wi-Fi, Visible Light Communication, Photodiode, LED, Wireless Communication

INTRODUCTION

Transmission of data from one place to another is one of the most important day-to-day activities. When multiple devices are connected ,the current wireless networks that connects to the internet are very slow . The fixed bandwidth available makes it very difficult to enjoy high data transfer rates and connect to a secure network as the number of devices that access the internet increases . But radio waves are only a small part of the spectrum available for data transfer. Li-Fi is a solution to this problem.

Li-Fi stands for Light-Fidelity. Li-Fi is a new paradigm for optical wireless technology. It provides unprecedented connectivity within a data-centric environment. The increasing demand for more bandwidths, faster and secure data transmission along with environmental and human friendly technology heralds the start of a change in wireless technology, a change from radio frequency to optical technologies. Li-Fi is transmission of data through illumination. Fiber optics technology is utilized for sending data through an LED light bulb (Fig. 1) that varies in intensity faster than the human eye can follow. Li-Fi is the optical version of Wi-Fi. Instead of Gigahertz radio waves , Li-Fi uses visible light for data transfer.

Fig. 1. Li-Fi bulb

LI-FI TECHNOLOGY

The idea of LiFi technology was first presented by Professor Harald Haas from University of Edinburgh, UK. In his TED Global talk on Visual Light Communication he mentioned, “If the LED is on, you transmit a digital 1; if it’s off you transmit a 0. The LEDs can be switched on and off very rapidly, which gives nice opportunities for transmitting data.” The process of switching on and off is completely undetectable to human eye. Power consumption of LED is very less when compared to fluorescent lamp or a light bulb. It consumes only about one-tenth the power as against the conventional methods of lighting. The lifetime of a Li-Fi communication is structured according to the IEEE 802 workgroup communication protocols. The aim is to establish a wireless network using visible light. The range of wavelength of visible light in an electromagnetic radiation is from about 390 to 700 nm and corresponds to a frequency band of 430-790 THz. The data is initially converted to electrical signal using some signal converter and

a microcontroller is used according to the converted signal which modulates the LED lamp off and on. The result is that the LED produces flicker which is hidden to human vision. A set of Photo Diodes convert the flickering light to digital data signal which can be filtered and amplified to get the desired Internet data and thus establishing a Li-Fi network.

Figure 2: Working Principle of LI-FI Technology

Li Fi is a potential solution to the global wireless spectrum shortage which uses Visible light communication (VLC). VLC is a data communication medium .Visible light between 400 THz (780 nm) and 800 THz (375 nm) is used as the optical carrier for data transmission as well as illumination. To transmit information wirelessly fast pulses of light is utilized . The important components of this communication system are i) a high brightness white LED, which acts as a communication source and ii) a silicon photodiode that shows good response to visible wavelength region serving as the receiving element. The LED can be switched on and off to generate digital data of 1s and 0s. By varying the flickering rate of the LED , data can be encoded in the light to generate a new data stream. So by modulating the LED light with the data signal, the LED illumination can be used as a source of communication. The LED output appears constant to the human eye because of the fast flickering rate. With appropriate multiplexing techniques a data rate of more than 100 Mbps can be attained by using high speed

LEDs. The data rate of VLC can be increased by parallel data transmission using a series of LEDs where each LED transmits a different data stream.

Figure 3: Environment with LI FI Technology

COMPARISON WITH WIFI

Li-Fi derived this name by virtue of the similarity to Wi-Fi. Wi-Fi works well for general wireless coverage within buildings. But Li-Fi is ideal for high density wireless data coverage inside a confined area or room and for relieving radio interference issues. A comparison of transfer speed of various wireless technologies is shown in Table 1.

TABLE I. WIRELESS TECHNOLOGY SPEEDS – A COMPARISON

Technology	Speed
Wi-Fi – IEEE 802.11n	150 Mbps
Bluetooth	3 Mbps
IrDA 4 Mbps	IrDA 4 Mbps
Li Fi	>1 Gbps

A. Disadvantages of Wi-Fi

The following are the basic drawbacks with radio waves:

i) **Capacity:** Wireless data is transmitted through radio waves which is expensive. The bandwidth is also limited . With the rapidly growing world and development of technologies like 3G, 4G and 5G we are running out of spectrum.

ii) **Efficiency:** There are 1.4 million cellular radio base stations that consume huge amount of energy. Most of the energy is used for cooling down the base station and not for transmission. So the efficiency of such base stations is only 5%.

iii) **Availability:** Availability of radio waves is a big problem facing today. It is not advisable to use mobile phones in aero planes and at places like petrochemical plants and petrol pumps.

iv) **Security:** Radio waves can penetrate through walls. They can be intercepted and misused which causes a major security concern for Wi-Fi.

B. Advantages of Li-Fi

Li-Fi technology is based on LEDs or in general light source for transferring data. The data transfer can be with the help of all kinds of light, no matter the part of the spectrum that they belong. Thus the light can belong to the invisible, ultraviolet or the visible part of the spectrum. The speed of the communication is more than sufficient for downloading movies, games, music in very less time. Li-Fi eliminates the limitations that have been put on the user by the Wi-Fi.

i) **Capacity:** Light has 10000 times wider bandwidth than radio waves and light sources are already installed. So Li-Fi has got better capacity and also the equipments are already available.

ii) **Efficiency:** Data transmission using Li-Fi is very cheap. LED lights consume less energy and are highly efficient.

iii) **Availability:** As light sources are present everywhere availability is not an issue. There are billions of light bulbs worldwide which simply needs to be replaced with LEDs for proper transmission of data.

iv) **Security:** Li-Fi is more secure as light waves do not penetrate through walls. So, they can't be intercepted and misused.

APPLICATIONS OF LI-FI

Applications of LiFi technology ranges from public internet access through street lamps to auto-piloted cars that use headlights for communication. Li-Fi applications can extend in areas where the Wi-Fi technology lacks like medical technology, power plants and various other areas. Wi-Fi is banned because of interference with the radio waves in aircrafts and hospitals . Here Li-Fi can be used safely. Street lamps can be transferred to Li-Fi lamps to transfer data and thus it will be possible to access internet at any public place . The future applications of Li-Fi are as follows:

i) **Education systems:** The latest technology that can provide fastest speed internet access is a Li-Fi. It can replace Wi-Fi at campuses and companies so that everyone can make use of Li-Fi with the same speed intended in that area.

ii) **Medical Applications:** Operation theatres -OTs do not allow Wi-Fi due to radiation concerns. Wi-Fi usage in hospitals interferes with mobile and pc which blocks the signals for monitoring equipments which may be hazardous to the health of the patients. Li-Fi can be used for accessing internet and to control medical equipments in OTs thus overcoming the hazards of Wi-Fi and making it tech savvy. It can even be beneficial for robotic surgeries and other automated procedures.

iii) **Internet in Aircrafts:** The passengers in aircrafts gets only low speed internet at a very high rate. Wi-Fi is not used because it may interfere with the pilot's navigational systems . In aircrafts Li-Fi can be used for data transmission. Li-Fi can provide high speed internet through every light source such as overhead reading bulb inside the airplane.

iv) **Underwater applications:** Underwater ROVs- Remotely Operated Vehicles, operate from large cables that supply the power and allow them to receive signals from their pilots above. The tether that is used in ROVs is not long enough to allow them to explore larger areas. ROVs would be much freer to explore ,if their wires were replaced with light — say from a submerged, high-powered lamp. They can also use their headlamps to communicate with each other, processing data and sending their findings periodically back to the surface . Li-Fi can work even in underwater where Wi-Fi fails completely, thus opening an endless opportunity for military operations.

v) **Disaster management:** In times of disaster such as earthquake or hurricanes , Li-Fi can be used as a powerful means of communication. Subway stations and tunnels, common dead zones for most emergency communications, will not be an obstruction for Li-Fi. For normal periods, Li-Fi bulbs could provide cheap high-speed Web access to every street corner.

vi) **Applications in sensitive areas:** Power plants need fast, inter-connected data systems for monitoring the grid integrity and core temperature. Wi-Fi and many other radiation types are bad for sensitive areas around the power plants. Li-Fi could offer safe connectivity for all areas of these sensitive locations which helps in saving money when compared to the present implemented solutions. Also, the pressure on own reserves of the power plant could be lessened. In petroleum or chemical plants where other transmission or frequencies could be hazardous , Li-Fi can be used.

vii) **Traffic management:** In traffic signals Li-Fi can be used to communicate with the LED lights of the cars which can help in managing the traffic in a better manner .This can reduce the accident numbers. LED car lights can alert drivers when other vehicles are too close.

h) **Technology replacement :** Li-Fi doesn't work using radio waves. So, it can be easily used in places where Bluetooth, infrared, Wi-Fi, etc. are banned.

CONCLUSION

Every bulb can be used to transmit data which will lead towards a cleaner, greener, safer and brighter future , if Li-Fi technology can be put into practical use. Li-Fi may solve issues such as the shortage of radio-frequency bandwidth . It is also aimed at creating new data communication channels with the use of existing equipment. Currently, the LI-FI concept is catching a great deal of interest as it provides an authentic and very efficient alternative to wireless devices which use radio spectrum.

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